

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS**AN EXPLORATION OF THE CRITICAL METHODS FOR IMPROVING DESIGN STAGE COST ESTIMATES OF BUILDING PROJECTS: A THEORETICAL LITERATURE-BASED STUDY**

Johnson Adafin¹, Elijah Ayodele², Kola Olayiwola³, Olufemi Daramola⁴

¹Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Construction Management Programme, The University of Auckland, 20 Symonds Street, Auckland 1142, New Zealand

²School of the Built Environment, The University of Salford, The Crescent, Salford, Lancashire M5 4WT, United Kingdom

³School of Computing, Engineering and Mathematics, Civil Engineering Programme, The University of Western Sydney, Penrith NSW 2751, Australia ⁴Department of Quantity Surveying, The Polytechnic, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

KEYWORDS: Design stage cost estimate, factors, methods, budgetary tool, cost certainty

ABSTRACT

Accuracy of early cost estimates is a major concern for clients and cost engineers. Several researchers have long expressed their concern about cost estimating inaccuracies by recognising that the accuracy achieved in cost estimating has been less than desirable. The essence of having accurate design stage cost estimate as a reliable budgetary tool is defeated if the factors that affect design stage cost estimating accuracy and the critical methods for improving the subject are not given adequate consideration in the estimation process. Hence, project objectives regarding cost, time and quality targets are threatened. This paper first identifies various factors affecting design stage cost estimating accuracy in construction practice. Also, it provides a review of the influencing methods for improving design stage cost estimating accuracy of building projects by demonstrating the theoretical context. The study is a literature-based theoretical exploration, and a preliminary part of an on-going doctoral research on the budgetary reliability of design stage elemental cost plan aimed at assessing the risk impacts on the variability between design stage elemental cost plan and tender sum. The outcome of the doctoral research will provide the platform at exploring causes of variability with a view to developing a predictive model which will help construction industry practitioners in New Zealand in coming up with a reliable and objective elemental cost plan that guarantees cost certainty. This particular study is a first step towards a comprehensive empirical research of securing design stage cost estimate as a reliable budgetary tool that guarantees cost certainty for building projects.

INTRODUCTION

The reliability of final tender sums depends on the accurate projections of baseline cost estimates developed at the design development stage of project development. However no matter how much care and effort is put into the preparation of design stage cost estimates, significant deviations are usually observed between these cost estimates and the final tender sum. This makes accurate predictions challenging for construction industry practitioners. The major attributable factors for the variability between the design stage cost estimate and final tender sum are risk elements that are inherent in construction project developments.

(Odeyinka et al., 2010) explained that the budgeted cost established at the pre-contract stage forms the basis of the final tender sum otherwise known as the contract sum, and this is the amount arrived at for the entire project. (Potts, 2008) suggested that most clients work within tight pre-defined budgets which are usually part of a larger overall scheme. If a budget or design cost estimate is exceeded, the whole scheme may fail. Pre-contract estimating produces the original budget and this forecasts the likely expenditure for the client. (Odeyinka et al., 2012) submitted that this budget should be used positively to make sure that the design stays within the scope of the original scheme. Moreover, from a pre-tender view, it can be justifiably concluded that design stage cost estimate anticipates and predicts final tender sum. Thus, budgetary reliability or performance depends on the degree of variability between the design stage cost estimate

prepared by the quantity surveyor and final tender sums submitted by the contracting firms. Similarly, it is concluded further that the observable deviation between the design stage cost estimate and final tender sum is due to the factors which are not only hard to predict but also difficult to manage. Hence, many budget overruns are due to circumstances observed as factors affecting the design stage cost estimating accuracy and an important issue is the ability to predict such factors and the impact they have on the project (Odeyinka et al., 2010). The concern of this research is to identify various factors responsible for the variability between the design stage cost estimate and final tender sum. Also, the conjecture of the study is to examine the critical methods for improving the design stage cost estimating accuracy of building projects.

The overall aim of this study is to signify the design stage cost estimating as a function of those factors that affect its accuracy in the estimation process, with a view to providing a review of the influencing methods for improving design stage cost estimating accuracy of building projects by demonstrating the theoretical context. This paper is intended as a preliminary literature review, prior to full research project aimed at developing a predictive model that will assist construction industry practitioners to have a better and reliable prediction of a final tender sum of building project from the design stage cost estimate.

Design Stage Cost Estimating

Traditional construction management practice divides the project procurement process into two: (1) the design phase, and (2) the construction phase. Cost estimating has tended to follow, very closely, this division (Ogunlana, 1989). However, it is pertinent to strengthen this division with conceptual planning phase which practically precedes these two foregoing phases whereby conceptual cost estimating is performed under inadequate information circumstances and incomplete work scope definition meant for crucial project decisions like funding approval. This contribution was further strengthened and opined in (Liu & Zhu, 2007) that a typical project under conventional procurement system can be divided into five stages: (1) the conceptual stage, (2) the design stage, (3) the tender stage, (4) the pre-construction stage, and (5) the build stage. According to them, specifically at the design stage, estimates start with preliminary estimates; cost estimates are continuously adjusted as design evolves; as design progresses, more detailed estimates are produced. The main objective for cost estimation here is evaluating the design feasibility within budget constraints.

Design stage cost estimating has significant relevance to design stage cost planning as both sit between the conceptual planning phase and tender action phase of development process, hence both are performed between the outline proposal / scheme design stage and detailed design / tender action stage in accordance with RIBA Plan of work specified in (Kirkham, 2007). Design stage cost estimating is the principal responsibility of the client's cost consultant: the quantity surveyor (for building projects) or the design engineer (for civil engineering works) (Ogunlana, 1989) in contrast to a definition credited to the *Nigerian Institute of Quantity Surveyors 2006* that a Quantity Surveyor is an expert professionally trained and experienced in the financial management of construction schemes regarding building, civil and heavy industrial engineering works, respecting the schemes in prospect and work in progress.

At this point, it is extremely significant to consider design stage cost estimation as a function closely intertwined with the design process as reported in Oyediran (1992) cited in (Adafin, 2000). The building design process is a complex interaction of skills, judgement, knowledge, information and time, which has as its objective the satisfaction of the client's brief (Kirkham, 2007) or demand for shelter within the overall needs of the society. The quantity surveyor, as a member of the design team is charged with providing information on costs so that the designers could know the cost implications of their decisions. Hence, according to Oyediran (1992) cited in (Adafin, 2000) there is therefore the need for integration of cost information and design variables; this calls for a team approach in building design and the adoption of the *Royal Institute of British Architects' (RIBA) Plan of work* for project development. However, (Ogunlana, 1989) stressed that the design team is not constrained to conform rigidly to the plan of work in practice. Meanwhile, the RIBA Plan of work is therefore devised to take cognizance of this team approach. Also, the plan of work is a systematized procedure for taking design decisions with accompanying data to be incorporated at various stages of the design evolution (Oyediran, 1992 cited in Adafin, 2000); this

clearly reflects chronological development of project and the way in which the design stage estimates relate to the plan of work and cost planning process as reported in (Seeley, 1996) and (Kirkham, 2007) meant for design team operation as stated below:

- Briefing: this comprises inception and feasibility stages;
- Sketch plan: also comprises outline proposals and scheme design stages;
- Working drawings: this involves (i) detailed design stage, (ii) production information stage, (iii) bills of quantities stage, (iv) tender action stage
- Site operation: this constitutes (i) project planning stage, (ii) operation on site stage, (iii) completion, and (iv) feedback

The conclusion drawn from this submission indicates that design stage cost estimate shares similar meaning with conceptual cost estimate except that the former takes place at various stages of design process, commencing from outline proposal to detailed design stage of development process. While the latter takes place at the early or conceptual planning stage of project development and is undertaken by the cost consultant. Therefore, design stage cost estimate is a forecast of the probable cost of a proposed building project and is produced only when some level of design information and project scope definition is available during the design stage, but tender documents are not available. The traditional estimating methods such as (1) functional unit, (2) superficial, (3) cube, (4) elemental cost analysis, (5) approximate quantities, (6) elemental estimating, (7) storey-enclosure, and (8) interpolation as documented in (Haron et al., 2001; Soutos & Lowe, 2005) cannot adequately deal with risk, and in trying to aid this area, several techniques of cost modelling such as (1) regression analysis, (2) montecarlo simulation, and (3) neural networks, were among those cost estimation techniques developed and integrated for conceptual and design stage cost estimation which utilize the latest advancement in science and technology (Sonmez, 2004; Soutos & Lowe, 2005). Meanwhile, contractors are only engaged in tender-based cost estimating, likewise the cost consultant at tender action stage as soon as the tendering process is set in motion.

Accuracy in Design Stage Cost Estimating

The view in construction management literature is that the accuracy of estimates should improve as design progresses. Thus, the estimator has more information on which to base predictions and project is better defined than at the early stages of design (Ogunlana, 1989). Ideally, the study in this section should reflect precisely cost estimating at detailed design stage of project development as this clearly demonstrates improvements by showing less values of error than at the previous conceptual and scheme design stages. Also, detailed design stage reflects the stage at which cost checking confirms full cost plan produced by the quantity surveyor, hence final cost plan at this stage could be compared with the final tender sum or contract sum.

With reference to Morrison (1984), (Odusami & Onukwube, 2008) defined accuracy of quantity surveyors' estimates as the deviation from the lowest acceptable tender received in competition for a project. Following (Lee et al., 2011) the accuracy of a design stage cost estimate can equally be defined as the difference between the actual cost and design cost estimate; the actual cost being the contract sum, while the design cost estimate represents the cost estimate prepared specifically at detailed design stage of project development, and can be measured by the error rate calculated from Equation (1):

$$\text{Error rate (\%)} = (| \text{Actual Cost} - \text{Design Cost Estimate} | / \text{Actual Cost}) \times 100.$$

According to (Barzandeh, 2011) the accuracy of a design stage cost estimate can be assessed in different ways depending on whether the figure for comparison is the tender, end product or final account. It is the degree to which a measurement or calculation deviates from its actual cost; therefore, estimating accuracy is an indication of the degree to which the final account or contract sum of a project may vary from the single point value used as the design stage cost estimate of the project. (Oladokun et al., 2011) evaluated estimating accuracy in terms of biases in estimates (error level) and measures of consistency (the degree of variation). They analysed data from 82 building projects in Nigeria. Prepared design cost estimates (QSEs) and contract sums (CSs) of the projects were obtained from the database of the quantity surveying firm

(source of the data). The data also included project type, sectors from which the projects emanated, and year of estimates/awards. The deviation of design cost estimates from contract sums (estimate bias “Error”) was calculated in percentage form using the formula below:

$$\text{Estimate bias (Error)} = \frac{(QSEs - CSs)}{CS} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Positive value of Estimate bias/Error (%) indicates overestimation of cost for QSEs while negative value implies an underestimation of cost for QSEs. Also, the consistency in the estimate was determined by calculating the coefficient of variation (CV) for all building projects in different categories using the following formula (Aibinu et al., 2011; ; Aibinu & Pasco, 2008; Oladokun et al., 2011):

$$CV = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation}}{\text{Mean Error}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Ideally, in purely deterministic world Skitmore and Picken (2000) concluded that costing the construction implication of design decisions is supposed to be accurate, taking into consideration the effects of time for completion, construction quality, and resale or letting values. However, this is not so in practical situation as noted in (Aibinu et al., 2011; Aibinu & Pasco, 2008; Oladokun et al., 2011; ; Pasco & Aibinu, 2008) because estimates are often prepared within a limited time-frame and without the aid of a finalised project design. Meanwhile, (Odusami & Onukwube, 2008) opined that design stage cost estimating is usually carried out by consultant quantity surveyor on behalf of his client and is an attempt to forecast contractor’s tender sum before the design is finalized or before tenders are received. It is therefore important that estimates have to be as accurate as possible since they form the basis for tender comparison or negotiation, and underestimation may lead to difficulty in award decisions, or in some cases unrealistic negotiation targets. To this end, they further maintained that Quantity Surveyors are tasked to improve on the accuracy of their design stage cost estimates in order to ensure clients’ satisfaction.

Factors Affecting the Accuracy of Design Stage Cost Estimating

Accuracy of early cost estimates is a major concern for clients and cost engineers. Though, several researchers have long expressed their concern about cost estimating inaccuracies by recognising that the accuracy achieved in cost estimating has been less than desirable (Ashworth and Skitmore, 1983; Ogunlana and Thorpe, 1987) cited in (Jafarzadeh, 2012). The essence of having accurate design stage cost estimate as a reliable budgetary tool is defeated if risk estimates are not incorporated or not properly evaluated if incorporated. Hence, project objectives regarding cost, time and quality targets are threatened as contingency is proportional to the risk present in a construction project.

In contrast to CIOB (1997) that the definition of construction cost estimating is the technical process of predicting costs of construction; Ashworth and Skitmore (1983) argued, as revealed in (Odusami & Onukwube, 2008) that cost estimating cannot be a precise technical and analytical process but is, to an extent, a subjective process. This argument as viewed by (Odusami & Onukwube, 2008) tends to suggest that estimators consider factors relevant to the successful execution of a project. Most important factors affecting contractors’ cost estimate according to (Enshassi et al., 2005) in their case study, are: client’s financial status, type of current contractor workload and project location. In addition, based on Akintoye’s (2000) findings, the most important factors identified as influencing project cost estimating practice include (1) complexity of design and construction, (2) scale and scope of construction, (3) method of construction, (4) tender period and market condition, (5) site constraints, (6) client’s financial position, (7) buildability, and (8) project location. He further concluded that those factors have a direct effect on productivity levels on site and performance of the construction project. In his work, he analysed 24 factors that influence project cost estimating practice, but his work and that of (Enshassi et al., 2005) only concentrated/focused on contractors. Meanwhile (Odusami & Onukwube, 2008), in their study, reported seven most important factors that affect the accuracy of pre-tender cost estimate in Nigeria based on the construction industry experience of consultant quantity surveyors, which include (1) expertise of cost consultants, (2) quality of information and flow requirements, (3) project team’s experience of the construction type, (4) tender period

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and market conditions, (5) extent of completion of pre-contract design, (6) complexity of design and construction, and (7) availability and supplies of labour and materials. In their work, they highlighted 21 factors but focused on the perspective of consultants. According to them, it is believed that these factors may have effect on the accuracy design stage cost estimate and taking them into consideration will definitely improve the accuracy of consultant quantity surveyor’s preliminary cost advice to his client.

In summary, making reference in agreement to a thorough review of the related literature, (Ogunlana & Thorpe, 1991) classified various factors affecting estimating accuracy into three broad categories as documented in (Jafarzadeh, 2012), being (1) project-based, (2) immediate environment-based, and (3) external environment-based categories. The first category reflected such factors as type, size, project duration, and the level of design information available. Factors included in the second category are number of bidders, ability of the estimator, local construction practices (i.e. geographical location of the project), resource availability, site access conditions, and price movements in the immediate environment. Finally, factors accommodated by the last category are industry structure, state of the market, and price movements in the external environment. A diagrammatical illustration of these categories and their contributing factors is represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Factors affecting cost estimating accuracy
Source: (Ogunlana and Thorpe, 1991; Jafarzadeh, 2012)

Improving Accuracy in Design Stage Cost Estimating

Central to cost-based competition is the capability to accurately predict the cost of delivering a project. Overestimated cost could result in misjudgement for the feasibility of a project, or loss of a contract to competitors. On the other hand, the contractor could incur significant losses from underestimated cost (Liu & Zhu, 2007). Similarly, design stage cost estimates are susceptible to inaccuracies because they are often prepared within a limited time frame, and without finalized project scope (Aibinu & Pasco, 2008). They further stressed that pursuing an underestimated project can lead to project failure; on the other hand, overestimation of a project during the design stage can lead to a viable project being dropped or re-tendered for when there is no bid close enough to permit project award. While improving the accuracy of design stage cost estimates is important; from experience the first recognized characteristic of design stage cost estimating is the fact that it is yet another inexact process based on inadequate project information and the frequently existing risks and uncertainties during the design stage. (Serpell, 2005) in his study noted that the discussion and analysis of such an early stage cost estimating problems has consistently indicated specific needs or resources that permeate the early stage cost estimating in its entirety, and that addresses any effort leading to an improvement in the accuracy of design stage cost estimates.

Design stage cost estimating is a very important facet of the services that can provided by a quantity surveyor. The accuracy of design stage cost estimates is important in terms of overall project success, and it forms a substantial part of quantity surveying firms' workload. According to (Pasco & Aibinu, 2008) cost estimates produced at the design stage of project development determine whether a project is continued or dropped. They proceeded that accuracy of design stage cost estimate is an important piece of information needed for decision-making at the pre-tender stage. This study therefore explores the concepts of accuracy in design stage cost estimating to opine the accuracy in design stage cost planning by demonstrating the theoretical context of the relationship between both of them.

To ascertain the methods of improving accuracy, the estimating process is analysed as illustrated in Figure 2; this explains quantity surveying activities in transforming design into estimated costs which reflect four principal elements that affect design stage cost estimating accuracy namely (Ling & Boo, 2001): (1) design data, (2) time availability, (3) estimating technique, and (4) cost data. In addition, estimating skill and experience of the quantity surveyor is equally important to be considered as an element that affects design stage cost estimating accuracy, as this factor determines the proficiency with which an estimating technique is used. Also, the estimator's skill or experience determines the success or failure on any estimating technique adopted.

Figure 2: Elements that affect the accuracy of design stage cost estimates
Source: Ling and Boo (2001)

An overview of previous studies suggested that a large number of methods have been identified as measures for improving accuracy of design cost estimates. In a study carried out in Singapore, (Ling & Boo, 2001) concluded that there has been no improvement in estimating accuracy over time. Meanwhile, 13 possible methods for improving estimating accuracy were identified and tested in the fieldwork. Based on their findings, the study outlined 9 methods as effective measures for improving estimating accuracy, out of which 3 methods were analysed as the most important measures for improving estimating accuracy. Those 9 methods are to: (1) ensure sufficient design information is available for estimating (H3), (2) check all assumptions with clients and consultants (H4), (3) ensure proper design documentation and information management (H1), (4) provide a realistic time frame for estimating activity (H6), (5) use more rigorous method of estimating (H7), (6) establish effective communication and co-ordination between members of project team (H2), (7) update cost database with new cost analyses and provide feedback for improving estimating accuracy (H13), (8) prepare estimates based on tender documents (H9), and (9) improve methods of selection, adjustments and application of cost data (H12). However, a possible shortfall exists in this research as an increase in cost planning and control activities during the design stage, as well as incorporating market sentiments and economic conditions into the estimate by way of simulations, probability and utility functions convincingly appear important and relevant to improving estimating accuracy. To a great extent, (Ling & Boo, 2001) equally agreed in their study that it is common for changes to be made to designs, hence it is necessary to review the design cost estimates, and undertake cost planning and cost control activities. They concluded that if such activities are done progressively, such problems as issuing variations which may give rise to other problems like claims are possibly averted or reduced. Similarly, they further agreed that incorporating market sentiments and economic conditions into the estimate can produce higher estimating accuracy, only that the use of simulations, probability and utility functions is highly theoretical and are more suitable for the academia than the industry as hypothesized in (Ling & Boo, 2001). Besides, other methods analysed by them are to: (10) establish formal feedback for

design and estimating activities (H5), (11) increase cost planning and control activities during design stage (H11), (12) quantify and price effects of risk (H10), and (13) incorporate market sentiments and economic conditions into the estimate by way of simulations, probability and utility functions.

In contrast to the foregoing study, (Pasco & Aibinu, 2008) opined that quantity surveyors in Australia only slightly agreed on the relative effectiveness of the 13 methods for improving the accuracy of design stage cost estimates as established in (Ling & Boo, 2001). The 3 most effective methods identified in this study are to: (1) ensure sufficient design information is available for estimating, (2) increase cost planning and control activities during the design stage, (3) check all assumptions with clients and consultants, out of 12 methods analysed. Other effective methods analysed in chronological order are to: (4) establish effective communication and co-ordination between members of the project team, (5) ensure proper design documentation, (6) update cost database with new cost analyses and provide feedback for improving estimate accuracy, (7) provide a realistic time frame for estimating activity, (8) incorporate other market sentiments and economic conditions into the estimate, (9) improve methods of selection, adjustments and application of cost data, (10) establish formal feedback for design and estimating activities, (11) use a more rigorous method of estimating, and (12) incorporate market sentiments and economic conditions into the estimate by way of simulations, probability and utility functions.

Similarly, (Ashworth, 2004) outlined three very important factors for improving design stage cost estimating accuracy which include: (1) an improvement in the quality of designer's information, since a vague design results only in an inaccurate estimate, (2) a reappraisal of the methods currently in use for estimating, and (3) to identify the qualities or attributes in the estimator or quantity surveyor which contribute towards accuracy in estimating, and to consider how these can be improved. In other words, qualities or attributes mentioned could be in terms of the skill and experience of the quantity surveyor involved in the estimating activity.

In another study in Australia, analysis of data from 56 building projects revealed in (Aibinu & Pasco, 2008) that the accuracy of design stage cost estimates has not improved over time. The Australian quantity surveyors perceived: (1) ensuring sufficient information is available at the time of estimating, as the most effective method of improving estimating (first); followed by (2) increased cost planning and control activities during the design stage (second), and (3) checking all assumptions with clients and consultants during the estimating period (third). Other effective methods, according to them include: (4) proper documentation of experience acquired in the estimation of projects, (5) reducing quantity surveying and cost engineering skill turnover, (6) incorporating market sentiments into estimates, (7) early involvement of the quantity surveyor at the brief stage of project development, and (8) probability estimation and simulation of past estimates. Based on their findings, these factors should help firms increase the accuracy of estimates for new projects undertaken by them. Thus, the result is similar to those established in (Ling & Boo, 2001) and (Pasco & Aibinu, 2008); the only difference perceived is the chronological order in which the methods or factors were arranged. In addition, these studies which have found universal acceptability and applicability suggested that there are a large number of effective methods that substantially influence improvement on the accuracy of design stage cost estimates. (Aibinu & Pasco, 2008) concluded that the similarities only indicate an international sentiment regarding methods of improving the accuracy of design stage cost estimates.

Research Methods

This study is a theoretical research based on literature review with a view to examining the critical methods for improving the accuracy of design stage cost estimating by demonstrating the theoretical context. In addition, the literature sources were accessed through databases which provided numerous academic journals and conference papers. Also, some textbooks found to be useful to the research process were referenced. A comprehensive literature survey was carried out towards securing design stage cost estimate as a reliable budgetary tool that guarantees cost for construction projects.

CONCLUSION

The aim of this paper is to provide a preliminary literature review, prior to a full research project aimed at developing a predictive model that will assist construction industry practitioners to have a better and reliable prediction of final tender sums of building projects from the design stage cost estimates. Extant literatures have indicated that certain circumstances observed as factors affecting design stage estimating accuracy have an impact on the deviations experienced during the design development stage between design stage cost estimates and final tender sums. The assessment of these identified factors and adequate consideration given to the critical methods for improving estimating accuracy could assist in determining the final tender sum from the design stage cost estimate. Thus, the review of relevant literature suggests that the essence of having a design stage cost estimate as a reliable budgetary tool that guarantees cost certainty for building projects is secured if those identified factors and critical methods for improving estimating accuracy are given adequate consideration in the estimation process.

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